

EVALUATION OF POWER CONTROL CONCEPTS USING THE PMAD SYSTEMS TEST BED

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Abstract

This paper provides a description of the Lewis Research Center's Power Management and Distribution (PMAD) Systems Test Bed and its use in the evaluation of control concepts applicable to the NASA Space Station Freedom Electric Power System (EPS). The space station power system will require a higher level of automated control and operation than is currently practiced by terrestrial utility power systems. The PMAD Systems Test Bed facility was constructed to allow testing of control hardware and software in an environment functionally similar to the space station EPS. Control hardware and software has been developed to allow operation of the Test Bed power system in a manner similar to a Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system employed by utility power systems for control. Descriptions of the hardware and software for this system are provided.

Control algorithms are integrated into the test bed in a three-step process. The Ada control software is run off-line on a separate computer with simulated data provided by a load flow program. The second step uses actual test bed data that is manually inputted to the off-line computer running the control software. Control action generated by the control software is implemented by an operator. Verification is completed after proper control action is obtained for the disturbance and the resulting control action returns the system to the normal operating state. The software is run on-line without operator intervention after verification. Descriptions of the System Security Monitor and Control software are provided.

Introduction

The primary purpose for the development of the PMAD System Test Bed was to address system issues associated with the distribution and control of multi-kilowatt power for the space station. The space station power system is totally different from any past aircraft or spacecraft power system because it is being designed with attributes similar to a terrestrial utility power system. This implies that the space station power system shall be secure under all conditions, provide power to a multitude of users who are guaranteed a certain power availability, power quality, and load independence, and can evolve and grow as space station needs require.

The PMAD Systems Test Bed has been configured as shown in Fig. 1 in order to properly address issues associated with utility type operation of the space station power system. Salient features of a power system, needed to achieve the aforementioned attributes, would include the following:

- a.) Multiple power sources
- b.) Multiple paths from sources to load centers
- c.) Power peaking capability for unscheduled load demands
- d.) Large ratio of maximum load to connected load (Diversity Factor)
- e.) System protection to minimize the effect of power system faults on power availability

Although the space station power system will utilize the technology base that has been established by terrestrial power systems there are major differences between earth based utility power systems and the space station power systems currently being designed [1].

The space station power system is a self-sufficient island with limited power sources and storage, and a predominance of power processors that condition and regulate the power for both primary and secondary distribution. This results in a "soft" source that must limit the current, during overload or fault conditions, to a value that will not result in loss of the power processor. Despite these differences the space station EPS is required to provide power with a total drop out time not to exceed 50 milli-sec. Because of this the space station power system must be capable of responding to a disturbance more rapidly than is currently practiced in terrestrial utility power systems.

The lack of a significant system technology base with this type of power system led to the development of the PMAD System Test Bed. The following is a partial list of the system issues that will be addressed using the test bed power system:

- 1.) Fault detection, isolation and reconfiguration
- 2.) Real and reactive power sharing between inverters
- 3.) End to end system voltage regulation
- 4.) Bus load assignments
- 5.) Energy management
- 6.) Contingency analysis for defensive control action

- 7.) Load interface specifications
- 8.) System startup and shutdown procedures
- 9.) System peaking procedures

PMAD Systems Test Bed Support Facility

The PMAD Systems Test Bed is located in building 5, Engine Research Building (ERB), at the NASA Lewis Research Center in Cleveland, Ohio. The test bed and its related support equipment occupy three test cells and a control room in ERB. This section provides a brief description of the unique facility that has been assembled.

As can be seen from Fig. 1 the facility is capable of supplying source power from dc to 1200Hz, 3 phase ac, and absorbing power from dc to 20kHz, single phase ac. A patch panel located with the sources allows the flexibility to patch either a dc power supply or a Solar Array Simulator (SAS) into the inverter and either the 1200Hz power amplifier or the Brayton Rotating Unit into the converter. The facility also provides measurement capability from dc to 200kHz ac for voltage, current, power, and phase angle. Facility control and data acquisition is performed using an Analog Devices Computer system that interfaces with the test bed hardware through a IEEE 488 data bus and to facility hardware through various analog and digital channels. The following is a list and description of the support equipment for the PMAD Systems Test Bed facility [2].

MACSYM FACILITY CONTROLLER - The MACSYM system consists of two separate microcomputers. A 150 unit which interfaces with the Power Management Controller (PMC) and allows manual control of all test bed hardware and display of hardware status. A 250 unit which interfaces to all loads, sources and instrumentation contains 78 A/D channels, 8 D/A channels, and 78 D/D channels. Facility control commands are sent from the 150 unit to the 250 unit via RS422 data bus and then to the appropriate source or load device.

BRAYTON ROTATING UNIT (BRU) - The BRU simulator is an air driven turbo- alternator, developed by the Garrett Corporation, that uses a modified Lundell machine as the generator unit. The unit rotates at 36,000 RPM and produces a 1200Hz, 3 phase, 208 V line to line voltage. The unit is rated at 18.75 kVA at a .8 power factor and has electrical control characteristics similar to the control expected for the solar dynamic units to be used on the space station.

POWER AMPLIFIERS - The power amplifiers are rated at 9kVA and can be configured in single or three phase. The output voltage is variable from 80 to 300Vac and the units were built by Industrial Test Equipment.

SOLAR ARRAY SIMULATOR (SAS) - The SAS, made by Abacus, simulates a photovoltaic array by duplicating the I-V characteristics of the array under steady state conditions. The SAS is rated at 75kW and is typically run at an open circuit voltage of 200Vdc.

DC POWER SUPPLY - The DC power supply is an 11kW, 220v unit built by Hewlett-Packard.

20kHz LOAD BANK - The 20kHz load bank is a 30kW resistive load that was assembled using immersion heaters and can be operated at high voltage (440Vac).

PROGRAMMABLE LOAD BANK - The programmable load bank, made by Energy Systems, is a 208V, 32kW, DC to 20kHz water cooled load bank made up of eight Power Absorption Modules (PAM) and two Power Control Modules (PCM). The PAM's can be set up to allow for constant current, power or resistance operation and they utilize power FET's to dissipate the power.

INSTRUMENTATION - Up to 26 points in the test bed can be monitored using wide band wattmeters from Norma (Model No. D5135, bandwidth to 400kHz), Valhalla (Model No. 2300, bandwidth to 20kHz), and Clark-Hess (Model Nos. 255, 258, bandwidth to 1MHz). All wattmeters have the capability to measure voltage, current, and power. Power factor measurements can also be obtained using the Norma wattmeters.

PMAD Systems Test Bed Description

As can be seen from Fig. 1 the power distribution system in the test bed consists of an inverter and a converter that are paralleled at the Main Bus Switching Assembly (MBSA), a ring transmission feeder that connects two Power Distribution and Control Units (PDCU), and several types of load receivers. The load receivers are connected to the main distribution system through step down transformers and Remote Power Controllers (RPC). A SAS is used to provide the DC input power for the inverter through a DC Remote Bus Isolator (RBI). A BRU simulator is used to provide three phase, 1200Hz AC input to the 1200Hz, 3 phase RBI which is connected to the source converter. All of these components have been developed through the Space Station Freedom Advanced Development Program and their characteristics are described in the following list.

DC REMOTE BUS ISOLATOR - The DC RBI is a bi-directional, current-limiting controlled switch. The DC RBI uses back-to-back transistors and can be set to limit current over a range from 0 to 150A at 200V. The DC RBI has a 1553b data interface that allows monitoring of the input voltage, current, current direction, switch and trip status and current-limit set point. The DC RBI was developed by Rocketdyne and Westinghouse.

1200Hz REMOTE BUS ISOLATOR - The 1200Hz RBI is a three-phase, four-wire, 208V, 50A controlled switch. This RBI uses back to back SCR's in parallel with an electro-mechanical relay in each line. An overcurrent trip point can be set for overload and fault protection. A 1553b data interface allows monitoring of the input and output voltage, current, power, switch and trip status, and overcurrent trip point. The switch will gang trip for single line or multiple line faults or overload. The 1200Hz RBI was developed by Rocketdyne and Westinghouse.

INVERTER - The inverter is a quasi-resonant, bi-directional, parallel unit that uses transistors to obtain a 20kHz, 440v, single phase, 10kW output. The transistors are arranged in a bridge with two of the transistors operating at a 50% duty cycle and the other two pulse width modulated. The inverter uses a clock to control the output frequency and control of output voltage is accomplished by controlling the tank energy. The inverter is capable of operating continuously into a fault at rated current. The inverter was developed by TRW.

CONVERTER - The converter is an identical unit to the inverter with the addition of an input three-phase rectifier and filter.

20kHz REMOTE BUS ISOLATOR - The 20kHz RBI is a controlled switch used in the main distribution system. The 20kHz RBI's used in the test bed are all rated at 440V, 50A, single phase. All RBI's communicate through a 1553b data bus and can monitor input and output voltage and current, output power and phase angle of input current, as well as over-current and differential set point, trip and switch status. All RBI's have the capability to trip after sensing an overcurrent or a differential current that exceeds the set point. Differential fault protection covers all fault types, line to neutral, line to ground, and neutral to ground. As with the 1200Hz RBI the switch implementation uses back-to-back SCR's in parallel with an electro-mechanical relay for both the line and the neutral. The 20kHz RBI's were developed by Rocketdyne and Westinghouse.

TRANSFORMERS - All step down transformers used in the test bed are rated at 25kVA, 440V input, 208V output. Transformers were developed by Westinghouse and TRW. The TRW transformers contain double shields to reduce noise coupling.

20kHz REMOTE POWER CONTROLLER The 20kHz RPC's are similar units to the 20kHz RBI's. All RPC's are rated at 208V, 25A., single phase and use back to back SCR's for switching the line and neutral. RPC monitoring is the same as the 20kHz RBI and is communicated through a 1553b data interface. Fault protection is implemented using overcurrent trip capability.

AC LOAD CONVERTER - The AC load converter uses a resonant circuit topology to convert from 20kHz, 208V to a variable lower frequency (0-200Hz), variable voltage (0-80V). The unit is rated at 1.5kw and was developed by TRW.

DC LOAD CONVERTER - The DC load converter also uses a resonant circuit topology to obtain 28Vdc output at a rated power of 1kW. This unit also was developed by TRW under the space station advanced development program.

MAIN BUS SWITCHING ASSEMBLY - The MBSA is one of the functional orbital replacement units that were developed for the test bed. The MBSA is used to monitor and control the main distribution system at the point where

the source inverter and converter are paralleled. The MBSA is divided into two busses with differential protection for both busses. The MBSA was developed by Rocketdyne.

POWER DISTRIBUTION AND CONTROL UNIT - The PDCU's are used to monitor and control the secondary distribution system and are functional representations of the orbital replacement units expected for the space station power system. The PDCU's are the equivalent of the substation in a utility power system. As in the MBSA the PDCU's contain a split bus which are protected using differential current trip. The PDCU was developed by Rocketdyne.

DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM - As can be observed from Fig. 1 the distribution system for the test bed utilizes a ring for the main distribution and radial feeds from the PDCU to all the loads. The main distribution lines use a flat cable designed by Gore [3] and all secondary cables are Litz power coax. The flat cable is rated at 440V, 68A and a total of 300 feet is utilized to connect from the source converters to all PDCU's. Another 200 feet of Litz coax is used in the secondary to connect loads and load converters to the power system.

The primary protection system in the test bed utilizes a hard-wired differential current trip for all main lines and overcurrent for all secondary lines. The distribution system was divided up into zones with boundaries of the zones determined by the location of the switchgear. All zones overlap at the switchgear defining the end of the adjacent zone. This provides protection to the entire test bed including any faults that could occur in any power hardware. Differential trip levels have been set typically at 7A and overcurrent trip levels are set to protect loads from significant overcurrents that could damage loads or load converters. A back-up protection system is implemented using software differential calculations performed in the local controller.

CONTROLLER NETWORK - The controller network for the test bed consists of five processors that are linked together using an Ethernet data bus. At the highest level in the control system hierarchy is the Power Management Controller (PMC) which coordinates all lower level controllers. The second tier controllers consist of two Power Distribution Controllers (PDC) which monitor the loads, a Main Bus Controller (MBC) which monitors the source paralleling node, and the Power Source Controller (PSC) which coordinates and monitors the inverter and converter. All second tier controllers (PSC, MBC, PDC) communicate with the lower level switchgear, inverter and converter through 1553b data busses.

All controllers in the test bed are Intel 86/35 single board computers with math coprocessors. Several generations of Ada software [4] have been written which allow communication through the different data busses, storage of power system data, and display of test bed status. This software resembles a SCADA system used by utility power companies and is the basic operating system for the test bed power system.

System Security Monitor

As was mentioned earlier the purpose of the PMAD Systems Test Bed was to address system issues associated with operation and control of the Space Station Freedom EPS. A System Security Monitor and Controller (SSMC) was developed [5] to allow for automated operation of the test bed power system. The SSMC was developed to take corrective action automatically in response to four kinds of disturbances. The following is a list of those disturbances in decreasing order of importance.

1. Switchgear status change
2. Transmission line overload or soft fault
3. Load overcurrents
4. Abnormally high or low voltages

The SSMC maintains a database of the test bed electrical network as shown in Fig. 2. All line, switch, and transformer parameter values are fixed in the database. The operating system software updates the database with information on all measured values and switch status. Using this information the SSMC is run periodically to determine if any of the disturbances listed above have occurred. A flow chart for the SSMC is shown in Fig. 3.

Two algorithms are essential to the operation of the SSMC, these are the state estimator and load flow. The state estimator is used to process the redundant data obtained from each monitored node in the test bed. A weighted least squares routine is used along with known Gaussian distributions of measurement error for each sensor to obtain a more accurate estimate of the power system state. The load flow algorithm is used to analyze any projected operating states given the load and distribution constraints that exist. This is essential for any contingency analysis that is performed so that defensive strategies can be obtained prior to any disturbance. These algorithms, because of their fundamental importance, will be the first to be integrated into the test bed power system.

Control Software Integration

Control software integration is accomplished through a three-step process. The first step involves the simulation of the test bed power system using the test bed topology and measured line parameters. A load flow program was then developed to calculate the operating state of the test bed for any load given the source power capability. The output of the load flow program represents the actual state of the power system without measurement error. The load flow calculations are then corrupted using a Gaussian noise source and these values are input to the SSMC as measured data. Disturbances can now be introduced into the simulation and the output data stream represents the actual data accumulated by the SCADA system and resident in the PMC database. An example of a typical output from the load flow algorithm before and after noise corruption is shown in Table 1. The simulated data is now used as input to the SSMC Ada software and disturbances are introduced

to verify proper control action. The output from the state estimator is also provided in Table 1. This step was completed prior to any cross compilation to the test bed target processors.

The second step in the integration procedure is to take steady-state test bed data accumulated in the database of the PMC and input the data to the SSMC. This will allow for test of the convergence of the state estimator and the load flow algorithms. Disturbances are now simulated using the test bed hardware and the resultant data fed into the SSMC. The outputs from the SSMC are checked for validity and then implemented manually to check the final state of the power system. If the proper state is obtained then the software is considered verified. This step will commence at the Lewis Research Center following completion of the cross-compilation of all SSMC software on to an Intel 386 processor.

The final step in the integration of the SSMC is on-line implementation. Each type of disturbance handled by the SSMC will be simulated using the test bed hardware and the transient response of the test bed power system with control will be recorded and used to aid in the design of future control algorithms for the test bed and Space Station Freedom EPS.

Conclusions

The PMAD Systems Test Bed can be used to verify and validate control algorithms similar to those that are currently envisioned for the Space Station Freedom. The process that has been described in this paper is expected to be followed when the control algorithms for the space station are integrated into the power system.

References

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FIGURE 1 PMAD SYSTEMS TEST BED SCHEMATIC

FIGURE 2 PMAD SYSTEMS TEST BED ELECTRICAL TRANSMISSION NETWORK DIAGRAM

FIGURE 3 SECURITY MONITOR AND CONTROL SOFTWARE

	LOAD FLOW			MEASUREMENTS			STATE ESTIMATOR		
	VOLTS	POWER	CURRENT	VOLTS	POWER	CURRENT	VOLTS	POWER	CURRENT
B1	0.9429	0.050	0.100	0.9392	0.0484	0.1013	0.9405	0.0498	0.0999
B2	0.9960	0.032	0.210	0.9916	0.0342	0.0235	0.9892	0.0321	0.0209
B3	1.0055	0.125	0.000	1.0014	0.1336	0.0004	1.0591	0.1250	0.0001
B4	1.0004	0.062	0.0125	1.0018	0.0697	0.0088	1.0003	0.0624	0.0125
B11	1.0135	-0.25	-0.121	1.0094	-.1421	-.0528	1.0132	-0.250	-.1214
B12	1.0100	-0.021	0.0833	1.0088	-.1317	0.0146	1.0102	-.0208	0.0832
L1a	1.0095	0.104	0.0876	1.0068	0.0937	0.0857	1.0091	0.1041	0.0876
L1b	1.0103	-0.104	-0.0767	1.0076	-.0938	-.0749	1.0110	-.1042	-.0767
L2a	1.0095	-0.022	0.0427	1.0068	0.0611	0.0477	1.0099	-.0219	0.0426
L2b	1.0093	0.0219	0.0075	1.0086	-.0612	0.0021	1.0092	0.0219	0.0074
L3a	1.0093	0.1657	0.0165	1.0086	-.1488	-.0042	1.0093	0.1656	-.0166
L3b	1.0104	-.1658	-.0029	1.0076	0.1487	0.0179	1.0105	-.1658	-.0028
L4a	1.0103	0.0207	-.0628	1.0076	0.1098	-.0682	1.0101	0.0207	0.0627
L4b	1.0100	-.0208	0.0833	1.0088	-.1317	0.0146	1.0108	-.0207	0.0833
L5a	1.0104	0.2493	0.1416	1.0076	0.1716	0.1234	1.0111	0.2492	0.1415
L5b	1.0135	-0.250	-.1214	1.0094	0.1421	-.5285	1.0128	-0.250	-.1214
L6a	1.0103	0.1669	0.2788	1.0076	0.0355	0.2749	1.0102	0.1668	0.2787
L7a	1.0095	-.0540	0.0211	1.0068	-.0534	0.0239	1.0099	-.0539	0.0211
L8a	1.0093	0.1289	0.0026	1.0086	0.1374	0.0106	1.0101	0.1288	0.0025

All values are per unit (p.u.) Base values : V= 440v , P= 60kW

Bx = Bus injection at bus x

Lxl = Line injection into line x at low bus end

Lxh = Line injection into line x at high bus end

TABLE 1 SIMULATED DISTRIBUTION NETWORK DATA